

STRATEGIC MULTI-ALIGNMENT AND ACTIVE NEUTRALITY: SAUDI ARABIA'S GROWING PARTNERSHIP WITH CHINA AND INDIA IN A CHANGING GEOPOLITICS

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Abstract:

This paper examines the change in Saudi Arabia's foreign policy against the backdrop of the relative decline of the American-led liberal international order, the US's waning interest in the Middle East, and the emergence of a multi-polar global order. Historically based on the long-standing "oil for security" paradigm and a security alliance with America, the Kingdom is increasingly pursuing a strategy of strategic multi-alignment by expanding its diplomatic and economic ties with emerging eastern powers, particularly China and India.

This recalibration is intrinsically linked to the domestic imperatives of Vision 2030 which prioritizes economic diversification, regional stability and enhanced global connectivity. The paper analyses Riyadh's evolving foreign policy within broader theoretical debates on middle power diplomacy, strategic hedging and economic statecraft. It also examines how Saudi Arabia's relationship with China has developed into a complete strategic alliance, driven by shared interests in energy security, infrastructure investment through the Belt and Road Initiative. Simultaneously, Saudi Arabia's relations with India have strengthened. Currently, the Saudi economy is increasingly receptive to Indian investors and professionals, enticing them to engage in expanding industries such as hospitality, tourism, infrastructure and IT. India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC) further demonstrate this alignment by offering improved connectivity and reciprocal benefits. Despite the growing US-China and China-India competition, Saudi Arabia aims to maximise strategic flexibility through multi-alignments by gaining more economic and diplomatic autonomy while maintaining its security dependency on the US.

Keyword: Strategic Multi-Alignment, Vision 2030, BRI, IMEC, Middle Power, Strategic Hedging, Active Neutrality, Strategic Autonomy

Introduction

Due to the major structural changes taking place in the contemporary international system, the US unipolar world is steadily crumbling and a more fractured and multi-polar order is forming. Within this evolving geopolitical context, states across the Global South particularly middle powers are recalibrating their foreign policies to secure greater strategic autonomy, economic resilience and international relevance (Efstathopoulos, 2023: 213-232). Saudi Arabia, which has long been regarded as a close ally of the US is at the forefront this change (Mansour, & Ahmed, 2024: 298-319). While maintaining its foundational security ties with Washington, Riyadh has increasingly embraced a foreign policy posture defined by strategic multi-alignment, aiming to deepen partnerships with a diverse set of global actors, most notably China and India (Hussain, 2016: 100-282).

Saudi's foreign policy evolution is not just a reaction to the changing global order, but it is also closely tied to its ambitious domestic transformation goal, Vision 2030, which was unveiled in 2016 under the leadership of Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman. Vision 2030 seeks to strengthen Saudi Arabia's economic integration with the rest of the world, encourage a competitive private sector, and lessen the Kingdom's reliance on oil. In this sense, foreign policy has evolved into a crucial component of domestic modernisation, serving as a means of securing technology and investment as well as establishing Saudi Arabia as a key hub in international infrastructure and trade networks (Demmelhuber, 2019: 109-124). Amid growing scepticism in Riyadh about the reliability and consistency of U.S. commitments to the region, exacerbated by episodes such as the 2011 Arab Spring, the 2021 withdrawal from Afghanistan and shifting US energy interests, the Kingdom has sought to hedge its stakes by expanding its diplomatic and economic outreach. While the United States remains Saudi Arabia's principal security guarantor, the diversification of partnerships reflects a broader strategy to enhance resilience in a multi-polar world where power is distributed among several centres (Vakil, 2025: 61-70).

Saudi Arabia's geographic location at the intersection of Africa, Asia, and Europe further shapes this approach, making it a strategic asset and an international player of growing importance. Saudi Arabia's expanding alliances with China and India, the two largest economies with the fastest rates of economic growth, are especially important in this regard. These engagements are not ad hoc or episodic but are part of a coherent and structured strategy of multi-alignment. China, Saudi Arabia's biggest commercial partner, provides a complementary partnership based on political alignment around the values of sovereignty and non-intervention, energy security, and massive infrastructural investment under BRI. The relationship between Saudi Arabia and China has developed into a comprehensive strategic alliance characterised by collaboration in fields including technology, the digital economy, renewable energy, and even the military. China's mediating role in facilitating the 2023 Saudi-Iran rapprochement further illustrates Beijing's growing influence in West Asian diplomacy and Riyadh's willingness to engage with multiple great powers for strategic gain (ibid, 61-70).

Simultaneously, Saudi-India relations have experienced extensive growth, underpinned by converging interests in trade, defence, technology and labour force. These ties have gained momentum through the strategic convergence of Saudi Arabia's "Look East" policy and India's "Look West" strategy. Another important element of this emerging partnership is India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC), which was unveiled at the 2023 G20 Summit and intends to increase connectivity between Asia, the Arabian Peninsula, and Europe. This initiative positions Saudi Arabia as a central logistical and economic hub, while providing India with vital access to Middle Eastern and European markets (Priya, & Quamar, 2025:25-42). Moreover, Saudi investments in India, particularly in energy, infrastructure and mining, illustrate Riyadh's intent to cultivate long-term economic interdependence with New Delhi (ibid).

These multi-directional engagements must be understood as part of a broader hedging strategy, through which Riyadh seeks to minimize strategic risks while maximizing its leverage on the international stage. Rather than aligning exclusively with one bloc or superpower, Saudi Arabia is pursuing a pragmatic, interest-driven diplomacy that allows it to benefit from multiple partnerships across often-competing global

poles. This approach is consistent with what scholars of international relations have termed middle power diplomacy, a strategy whereby states of intermediate power engage in niche diplomacy, multilateralism and coalition-building to safeguard their sovereignty and advance national interests (Chaziza, & Lutmar, 2025). This approach is further supported by the Kingdom's involvement in international organisations like BRICS, SCO and G20, as well as its leadership in these groups (Vakil, 2025: 61-70). These forums provide Saudi Arabia with avenues to influence global norms, participate in shaping economic and security architectures and amplify its voice as a regional and global stakeholder. Concurrently, Riyadh has taken on a more active role in regional diplomacy, hosting high-level summits, mediating conflicts and engaging in dialogue with traditional adversaries like Iran and Qatar (Chaziza, & Lutmar, 2025). The shift from military interventionism to diplomatic engagement represents a significant transformation in Saudi Arabia's regional posture, reflective of its growing international ambition. Furthermore, Saudi Arabia's foreign policy realignment is also driven by structural factors and strategic necessity. The volatility of global energy markets, the imperatives of climate change and the rapid technological disruptions of the 21st century necessitate a more diversified and adaptive international strategy. As such, Riyadh has invested heavily in green technologies, such as hydrogen and solar energy, through initiatives like Neom and the Saudi Green Initiative, while partnering with technologically advanced economies in Asia and Europe (Priya, & Quamar, 2025:25-42). By taking these actions, Saudi Arabia is becoming more appealing to foreign businesses and key partners while also supporting global sustainability goals.

The multi-alignment policy of Saudi Arabia is not without its difficulties. The growing rivalry between China and United States necessitates cautious diplomatic adjustment and presents entanglement dangers. Similarly, the border tensions and strategic competition between India and China could complicate Saudi Arabia's balancing act. The Kingdom must also navigate persistent criticisms on human rights, democratic accountability, and transparency from its Western partners - issues that could hinder its soft power projection and global legitimacy. Nonetheless, the Saudi leadership appears committed to advancing a foreign policy doctrine that prioritizes national interests, sovereign autonomy, and diversified engagement (Demmelhuber, 2019: 109-124).

In sum, Saudi Arabia's evolving relationships with China and India serve as illustrative cases of a broader strategic transition in Riyadh's foreign policy. These partnerships reflect a deliberate effort to reposition the Kingdom as a key player in a multi-polar world- one that is no longer content with a singular alliance but instead seeks influence through diversification, balance and pragmatic diplomacy. The paper will explore the historical evolution, structural drivers and strategic implications of Saudi Arabia's multi-alignment strategy, with particular focus on its engagements with China and India. It will also evaluate how this approach strengthens Vision 2030's internal objectives, changes the balance of power in the region and reinterprets Saudi Arabia's role in the global order.

Active Neutrality and Multi-Alignment for Strategic Autonomy

Saudi Arabia and United States have had a close connection for a long time because of the stability, economic possibilities and security guarantees that US offers (Samaan, 2019: 10-11). Historically, the "oil-for-security" relationship has been based on the United States granting Saudi Arabia military protection and advanced defensive capabilities in exchange for a steady oil supply and political alignment in the Middle East (Mansour, & Ahmed, 2024: 298-319). The U.S-Saudi partnership has been evident through extensive arms sales, intelligence cooperation, and joint counterterrorism efforts. Their economic ties also remain strong, particularly in infrastructure and energy sectors. With an estimated defence budget of \$69.1 billion, Saudi Arabia is the Middle East's largest military spender, according to *The Military Balance* report (Wall, 2024: 335). Despite this high spending, the Kingdom remains heavily dependent on the United States for its defence needs, with around 78% of its military acquisitions between 2018 and 2022 sourced from the U.S (ibid:335). Additionally, approximately 2,700 U.S. military personnel are currently deployed in Saudi Arabia, offering training and operational assistance to the Kingdom's armed forces (ibid: 335). Beyond capacity-building, their presence plays a strategic role in deterring potential threats from Iran and its affiliated proxy groups, reinforcing Saudi national security and broader regional stability.

Despite long-standing cooperation, the U.S.-Saudi relationship has been marked by recurring tensions. A key point of friction lies in their differing approaches to the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, with Saudi Arabia

advocating a two-state solution, while the U.S maintains strong support for Israel. Relations have further cooled since 2019 due to America's growing energy independence and increased focus on domestic priorities. During the Obama administration, which placed a strong emphasis on strategic competition with China and Russia, Saudi officials felt that the United States was gradually withdrawing from the Middle East. Subsequent administrations under Trump and Biden largely continued this shift, contributing to Riyadh's frustration (Mansour, & Ahmed, 2024: 298-319). A number of significant problems have led to an increase in tensions between Saudi Arabia and US. The United States' support of protest movements during the 2011 Arab revolutions appeared to contradict long-standing allies, which infuriated Riyadh (Gause, 2023). The rushed U.S. withdrawal from Afghanistan in 2021 and its unclear approach to Middle East security added to Saudi concerns. The U.S. Congress's condemnation of Saudi's human rights record and its role in the Yemen war has further caused disagreement. Like other countries in the region, Saudi Arabia is worried about the US unpredictable actions (Vakil, 2025: 61-70).

Even though Saudi Arabia has strong security ties with the U.S, it has made independent decisions in trade, oil and regional matters. In 2022, when the U.S. asked Saudi Arabia to raise oil production during the Ukraine war, it chose instead to cut production with OPEC+, which helped Russia. The U.S. saw this as a political move. Saudi Arabia calls its policy "active neutrality," meaning it tries to balance different sides (ibid). In 2023, it invited Ukraine's President Zelenskyy to the Arab League summit and hosted a peace meeting in Jeddah. At the same time, Saudi ties with China have grown, with China now being the primary buyer of Saudi exports (ibid).

Saudi Arabia's crude oil shipments to China totalled \$54.3 billion in 2023, according to IMF figures, which is three times more than its exports to the United States (International Monetary Fund, 2024). Saudi's Vision 2030 and China Belt and Road Initiative are closely related strategically, especially in the fields of technology, infrastructure, and hydrogen energy. In an effort to strengthen military ties, China is helping Saudi Arabia develop ballistic missiles. Additionally, China mediated the March 2023 Saudi-Iranian accord (Vakil, 2025: 61-70). Saudi Arabia, like other Arab leaders, values China's approach of refraining from meddling in domestic matters. Although their alliance is

expected to expand, Saudi Arabia believes China's capacity to manage regional disputes and adopt firm stances in Middle East rivalry is limited (She, 2024).

Despite strengthening ties with China, Saudi Arabia continues to seek security guarantees from the United States through a formal defence agreement to stabilize their relationship. President Joe Biden has tried to balance strategic interests with human rights concerns in his approach to Saudi Arabia. Despite his early criticism, particularly following the murder of journalist Jamal Khashoggi in 2018, Biden travelled to the Kingdom in July 2022 to talk about important topics like energy, regional security, and economic relations (Coates Ulrichsen, 2023). This visit resulted in the "Jeddah Communique," which reaffirmed cooperation in energy, defence, and investment. The U.S. also backed Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 and its World Expo 2030 world's fair (ibid). Biden's shifting stance reflects a move from strong criticism to cautious engagement based on broader global and regional priorities. During his presidency, Donald J. Trump highlighted the significance of U.S.-Saudi ties during two significant trips to Saudi Arabia. His first visit in May 2017, also his first foreign trip as president, led to a \$110 billion arms deal and the creation of the Global Centre for Combating Extremist Ideology (Agha, 2017). Trump urged for coordinated measures against terrorism and extremism at the Arab Islamic American Summit, which brought together leaders from more than 50 countries with a majority of Muslims. This showed increased collaboration in the areas of security, counterterrorism, and diplomacy (ibid). President Trump's 2025 visit to Saudi Arabia, his first international trip after re-election, reaffirmed the deep strategic ties between Washington and Riyadh. Highlighting Saudi Arabia's central role in U.S. foreign policy, the visit featured a record \$142 billion defence deal and a \$600 billion Saudi investment pledge in key U.S. sectors like energy, tech, and infrastructure (Mosly, 2025).

Despite maintaining strong ties with the United States, Saudi Arabia is actively pursuing a multi-polar foreign policy. While its security framework remains anchored in Western alliances, particularly with Washington, its economic relations are increasingly shifting eastward, notably toward China and India (Vakil, 2025: 61-70). This strategy reflects Riyadh's aim to safeguard its national interests through diversified global partnerships in a more balanced international system. In this evolving multi-polar context, Saudi Arabia seeks greater strategic autonomy by carefully

managing its relationships with key global powers, including the U.S, China, Russia, India and various Global South nations, with Europe playing a more limited role (ibid). Saudi Investment Minister Khalid al-Falih has emphasised that Saudi Arabia views its relations with China and the US as complementary rather than rivalry (Turak, 2023). Additionally, he emphasised Saudi Arabia's and China's increasing convergence, both of which are viewed as significant actors in the new multi-polar global order (Vakil, 2025: 61-70).

Saudi Arabia aims to establish itself as a key regional convenor in West Asia and to lead the Islamic world by establishing itself as a rising middle power with substantial economic clout. (Mansour, & Ahmed, 2024: 298-319). The pragmatic multi-alignment strategy, which aims to increase geopolitical flexibility by interacting with other global powers, is a key component of foreign policy of Saudi Arab. Maintaining a careful geopolitical balance, maintaining ties with Western allies while expanding relations with emerging actors like Russia, China and India; prioritising diplomatic reconciliation with regional rivals like Iran and Qatar; and advancing economic diplomacy through deeper trade and investment relations with Asian powers like China, Japan, South Korea and India are the three main pillars of this strategy (Chaziza & Lutmar, 2025). This reflects Saudi Arabia's nuanced navigation of a complex multi-polar global order. Layla Ali (2022) similarly argued that Saudi Arabia is adopting a flexible and wide-ranging foreign policy focused on economic diversification, regional peace, and maintaining balanced relations with major global powers. In adapting to shifts in the international order, Riyadh is using its economic power, diplomatic reach, and strategic location to protect its national interests and manage global challenges. This strategy is grounded in five key pillars: maintaining balanced ties with global powers (strategic multi-alignment), advancing economic diversification, engaging in proactive diplomacy, ensuring regional peace and stability, and safeguarding the Kingdom's sovereignty (ibid).

Since its introduction in 2016, Vision 2030 has functioned not only as a domestic reform strategy but also as a key framework guiding Saudi Arabia's foreign policy. It prioritizes economic diversification and deeper integration into the global economy. To support long-term growth and attract foreign investment, the Kingdom has placed strong emphasis on cultivating stable international partnerships. Diplomatic efforts have

aimed at building an investor-friendly climate and strengthening trade and infrastructure links. Saudi's robust involvement in initiatives such as the China's BRI and IMEC reflects its broader development objectives and solidifies its standing as a major international economic centre (Chaziza & Lutmar, 2025). During the G20 Summit in September 2023, Saudi Arabia and several other countries signed a Memorandum of Understanding on IMEC. Alongside its ties with major global powers, Riyadh is also strengthening relations with emerging markets and countries in the Global South (Priya, & Quamar, 2025:25-42). This strategy reflects not a shift away from any single partner, but a broader effort to diversify international partnerships in line with changing strategic needs (Vakil, 2025: 61-70).

Saudi Arabia is exhibiting its strategic objective to enhance diplomatic adaptability and play a more active role in establishing global economic and security frameworks by actively engaging in multilateral organisations such as SCO, BRICS and the G20 (Chaziza & Lutmar, 2025). The Kingdom has expanded its overseas partnerships and refocused as part of this broader strategy. It has strengthened ties with China through participation in BRICS and SCO, expanded cooperation with Russia through OPEC+ and intensified strategic engagement with India while maintaining strong security and economic ties with the US and Europe (ibid). Saudi Arabia has demonstrated leadership in the region by hosting significant multilateral summits, such as the GCC-ASEAN and Arab League-CARICOM meetings. Additionally, it has been actively engaged in regional diplomacy and conflict resolution, mediating the Qatar issue and promoting discussions on Syria, Sudan, and Gaza (ibid).

Over the past three decades, Saudi Arabia has provided more than USD 134 billion in humanitarian aid to 172 nations, significantly boosting its soft power, particularly in the Global South (ibid). Its influence over the Muslim world is further cemented by its leadership roles in Islamic institutions such as the Organisation of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) and the Islamic Development Bank. In order to establish itself as a new player in global climate governance, the Kingdom is simultaneously striking a balance between its status as a significant producer of fossil fuels and sustainability programs like Neom and the Saudi Green Initiative (Priya, & Quamar, 2025:25-42). In short, Saudi Arabia's foreign policy in the twenty-first century has moved away from military and ideological focus and towards interest-based, pragmatic diplomacy.

Under Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman, Saudi Arabia is strengthening its relations with the US, China, Russia, India, and other countries as part of a balanced foreign strategy. This approach supports the Kingdom's independence in international affairs while emphasising regional stability and economic cooperation, both of which are essential to its standing abroad and its internal development objectives (ibid).

Saudi's Look East Outreach: Deepening Partnership with China and India

As mentioned above, Saudi's "Look East" policy denotes a calculated tactical shift in foreign policy, aimed at diversifying its economic and geopolitical engagements in response to changing global dynamics. This policy realignment is situated within the broader context of the Kingdom's Vision 2030 goals, which emphasize reducing dependency on oil exports, fostering private sector growth, and attracting diversified foreign investment (Singh, 2023). A key driver of this eastern pivot is the gradual erosion of U.S-Saudi strategic relations, catalyzed by what can be identified as two major miscalculations by recent U.S. administrations. First, the Biden administration's rash decision that the Gulf's importance in the world energy landscape was diminished by American shale oil production led to the region being de-prioritized. Second, Washington underestimated the willingness and capacity of other global powers, particularly China, to fill the strategic vacuum left by its retrenchment from the Middle East (Mansour, & Ahmed, 2024: 307). In this evolving geopolitical context, Saudi Arabia has significantly deepened its engagements with China and India, two major Asian powers. The Saudi-China partnership is characterized by energy interdependence, infrastructure and technological cooperation, and shared adherence to principles of non-interference and sovereignty. Saudi Arabia's development goals under Vision 2030 are closely aligned with the BRI, expanding the opportunity for long-term strategic cooperation (Singh, 2023).

Parallely, the Saudi-India relationship has expanded across sectors such as energy security, infrastructure, investment, defense, technology and counterterrorism. India's large expatriate population in the Gulf and its growing economic stature make it a vital component of Riyadh's eastward policy shift. The convergence of "Look West" of India and "Look East" of KSA policies has facilitated synergistic cooperation,

exemplified by initiatives such as IMEC (Chen, & Liu, 2025). Collectively, these eastern partnerships reflect Saudi Arabia's evolving role as a strategically autonomous middle power in a multi-polar international order. The Kingdom's foreign policy today emphasizes pragmatic multi-alignment, reducing overreliance on traditional Western allies while leveraging opportunities with emerging global players to secure long-term national and regional interests (Singh, 2023).

Over the past three and a half decades, China and Saudi's bilateral partnerships have grown meaningfully and steadily since the official inauguration of diplomatic relations in July 1990 (Jonathan Fulton, 2020: 516 - 27). Frequent political interactions and ongoing cultural exchanges have reinforced the strong foundation of energy collaboration and trade relations between the two nations (Duan & Aldamer, 2022). Additionally, both countries have emphasised the significance of increasing bilateral investment and have committed to aligning Saudi Vision 2030 with China's BRI in order to further their respective development goals. In recent years, bilateral dialogues have also increasingly incorporated discussions on security and strategic cooperation. Importantly, the declaration of the diplomatic rapprochement between Iran and Saudi in Beijing in March 2023 demonstrated the extent of confidence that has grown between the two countries over time (Quamar, 2025).

The final Arab country to formally establish diplomatic ties with the People's Republic of China was Saudi Arabia, which did so in July 1990. This marked the beginning of a growing partnership across political, economic, and strategic areas (Shichor, 1979: 9-20). Saudi Arabia's strong anti-communist attitude during the Cold War era caused it to be reluctant to open diplomatic ties with China. But over time, a number of internal and international events made it easier for relations to normalise. The Sino-Soviet split in the 1960s, the rapprochement between China and the United States in the 1970s, and China's adoption of structural economic reforms in the 1980s all contributed to improved relations between Riyadh and Beijing. This diplomatic change was further reinforced by China's determination to put economic development ahead of ideological conflict (Huwaidin, 2002: 217-219).

During the 1980s, Saudi Arabia encountered mounting security threats, particularly from Iran amid the Iran-Iraq War and from Israel, which had

demonstrated its military capabilities through strikes on both Iraqi and Palestinian targets. Confronted with the reluctance of its traditional Western allies to supply medium-range ballistic missiles for deterrence purposes, King Fahd and his defence minister initiated covert negotiations with China. This culminated in a 1986 agreement under which China provided Saudi Arabia with 50 CSS-2 ballistic missiles (Mansour, & Ahmed, 2024: 298-319). These missiles were clandestinely deployed and operated by Saudi personnel who had been trained by Chinese experts (ibid: 298-319). The formal inauguration of diplomatic relations between Saudi Arabia and China in 1990 was sparked by this secret missile pact, which in turn enabled the swift growth of bilateral trade. In the years that followed, China became the largest importer of Saudi oil, with the Kingdom consistently ranking as China's leading energy supplier, occasionally surpassed only by Russia. As trade relations deepened, Saudi Arabia demonstrated a growing interest in strengthening high-level diplomatic engagement with Beijing (ibid).

In a notable departure from precedent, King Abdullah selected China as the destination for his first official foreign visit in 2006, indicating a strategic shift away from Saudi Arabia's traditional alignment with Western allies (She, 2024: 805-814). This visit marked a dramatic shift in Saudi foreign policy, demonstrating a conscious attempt to expand its global alliances beyond conventional Western allies by establishing closer ties with emerging Asian powers. This strategy became a defining characteristic of the Kingdom's "Look East" policy (Yamada, 2015: 121-139). Since 2006, there has been a consistent flow of high-level official exchanges, which has demonstrated the leadership's ongoing dedication to enhancing bilateral relations. A major turning point in Saudi-Chinese relations was reached in January 2016 when President Xi Jinping visited Riyadh and the two countries inked the Comprehensive Strategic Partnership Agreement, the highest level of diplomatic interaction. This agreement established the foundation for broad cooperation in the political, economic, cultural, military and security spheres and marked China's official acknowledgement of Saudi Arabia as a crucial Middle Eastern ally (Mansour, & Ahmed, 2024: 298-319). The joint communiqué reaffirmed both countries commitment to enhancing cooperation across bilateral, regional, and international spheres. The High-Level Joint Committee (HLJC) was created to assist

with this. Chinese Ambassador Li Huaxin called Saudi Arabia a “powerful ally” and “strategic partner” in 2019 (Nugali, 2019).

Two of the most notable recent visits are that of President Xi Jinping to Saudi Arabia in December 2022 and Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman to China in February 2019. These high-level interactions have had a major impact on how the two nations political, economic, and strategic cooperation has developed (Quamar, 2025). Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman’s 2019 visit to China was intended to improve bilateral relations amid the current U.S.-China trade war and the tense U.S.-Saudi ties that followed the Khashoggi incident. This intent was reflected in Energy Minister Khalid Al-Falih’s remarks highlighting the cultural compatibility between Saudi Arabia and China (Mansour, & Ahmed, 2024: 298-319). The visit also reflected Saudi Arabia’s strategic pivot towards Asia, as evidenced by Prince Mohammed’s tour of India, Pakistan, and China (Zhiqiang, 2019) One of the visit’s main results was the agreement to expedite the completion of an implementation plan that would integrate Saudi’s Vision 2030 with China BRI (Quamar, 2025).

In an effort to deepen bilateral relations, Chinese President Xi Jinping made a state visit to Saudi Arabia in December 2022. He was present at both the first China-GCC and the first China-Arab States summits, which took place in Riyadh. China praised the visit as a “historic turning point” in the history of the Arab-Chinese relationship (Mansour, & Ahmed, 2024: 298-319). During the visit, a Comprehensive Strategic Partnership (CSP) agreement was inked, adding to its symbolic significance. Discussions focused on strengthening strategic and economic collaboration, and the visit resulted in bilateral agreements worth over US\$30 billion (Qamar, 2025). The two nations have maintained their engagement through regular high-level political encounters ever since. Notably, Premier Li Qiang visited Riyadh in September 2024, and Saudi Foreign Minister Faisal bin Farhan came to Beijing in May 2024 for the 10th Ministerial Conference of the China-Arab States Cooperation Forum (ibid). Both bilateral and international venues have seen a number of ministerial-level interactions. For instance, Saudi Foreign Minister Faisal bin Farhan and his Chinese counterpart Qin Gang met in March 2023 in New Delhi for the G20 Foreign Minister’s Meeting (ibid).

Although roughly 75% of Saudi Arabia's total arms imports come from the United States, the Kingdom feels that Washington is not providing enough support, which falls short of its expectations (ibid). Between 2019 and 2024, China rose to become the world's fourth-largest arms exporter, indicating its growing sway over the international security arena (ibid). China's military exports to Saudi Arabia were worth about US\$80 million in 2020 and 2021, demonstrating a consistent, albeit limited, defence cooperation between the two nations (Ali, 2022). With a 400% growth in arms exports to Saudi Arabia between 2011–2015 and 2016-2020, China's defence cooperation with Saudi Arabia has grown significantly (ibid). Saudi Arabia purchased Chinese Wing Loong II drones in 2017. It later inked an agreement with China in March 2022 to collaborate on the design and construction of these drones in the Kingdom (Qamar, 2025). Saudi Defence Minister Khalid bin Salman travelled to China in June 2024 to talk about strengthening their military and defence relations (ibid). Beyond a doubt, Saudi Arabia's biggest defence and security ally is still the United States. US continued military presence in the Gulf significantly improves the stability of the Gulf and West Asia overall, as well as Saudi Arabia's national security. In order to avoid endangering its strategic corporation with America, Saudi Arabia has therefore increased its defence cooperation with China, although this cooperation is probably going to stay restricted (ibid).

Economic cooperation serves as the foundation of Sino-Saudi relations. By the early 2010s, Saudi Arabia's largest commercial partner was China. In 2021, bilateral commerce was worth \$87.3 billion, greater than the total amount of Saudi Arabia's trade with the US (\$24.8 billion) and the EU (\$53.1 billion) (She, 2024: 805-814). China and Saudi Arabia's bilateral commerce was valued at US\$107 billion in 2023, a minor decrease from the US\$116 billion in 2022 (Qamar, 2025). China and Saudi Arabia have expanded their cooperation into emerging sectors such as renewable energy, 5G technology, and biopharmaceuticals. These growing economic ties and mutual benefits have become the primary drivers of their deepening relationship in recent years (She, 2024: 805-814). China and Saudi Arabia regularly exchange delegations to boost trade in line with the BRI and Vision 2030 goals (Qamar, 2025). In August 2024, Saudi Arabia's Public Investment Fund (PIF) signed a Memorandum of Understanding with six major Chinese financial institutions, including the Bank of China and the Export-Import Bank of

China, to support investments reaching US\$50 billion (ibid). This underscores the expanding two-way investment flow between the two nations. Chinese investment in Saudi Arabia has increased and there are currently about 750 Chinese businesses operating in sectors like petrochemicals, energy and construction. Aramco and China National Building Material Group Co. inked a five-year contract in September 2024 to collaborate on industrial development and sophisticated materials (ibid).

Supply chains, digital technology, renewable energy, tourism, and education are just a few of the areas where China and Saudi Arabia have already worked together, and there is still much space for more cooperation. President Xi said in an interview with Crown Prince Mohammed that China supports Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030, the Green Middle East initiative, and other important projects. He added that China will keep supporting Saudi Arabia's industrial development and economic diversification (Niu & Wang, 2023: 15-30). The King Abdullah Petroleum Studies and Research Centre released a study in March 2019 with the title "Deepening Cooperation between Saudi Arabia and China". By pointing out crucial areas for strategic cooperation and making policy recommendations, the document underlines Saudi's aim to strengthen its ties with China (Cengiz, 2020: 51-67).

Despite strong progress in Saudi-China relations, challenges remain. U.S. pressure is a major factor, as the U.S. still dominates Gulf security and is wary of China's growing role. Tensions with Iran also complicate China's balancing act between Riyadh and Tehran. Rivalries within the Gulf add further difficulty (She, 2024). Still, the relationship is stable and pragmatic, with Saudi Arabia pursuing a strategy of hedging. China's involvement in the Saudi-Iran agreement demonstrates how this supports regional diplomacy while enabling both parties to avoid direct confrontation with the West. Cultural and educational ties have also grown, with more exchanges in language, education, and the arts (Qamar, 2025).

Equivalent to Saudi Arabia's outreach to China under its Look East policy, India has also emerged as a key strategic partner amid shifting global geopolitics. In addition to being a vital economic partner, especially in energy trade and infrastructure investment, the Kingdom

views India as a significant contributor to regional security and connectivity efforts such as IIMEC (Priya, & Quamar, 2025:25-42). This dual engagement reflects Riyadh's broader strategy of multi-alignment, balancing its ties with major Asian powers to enhance strategic autonomy and national development goals (ibid).

India and Saudi Arabia have shared economic and cultural ties for centuries. Through high-level visits and expanding cooperation, the two nations have gradually strengthened their ties since establishing diplomatic relations in 1947. King Saud's visit to India in 1955, followed by Prime Minister Nehru's visit to Saudi Arabia in 1956, helped lay the foundation. Prime Minister Indira Gandhi's 1982 visit to Saudi Arabia to strengthen ties was another significant event (Hussain, 2023: 1-16). However, the India-Saudi relationship faced major challenges due to various geopolitical, ideological, and regional factors. During the Cold War, India followed a non-aligned path and had close ties with the Soviet Union, while Saudi Arabia aligned itself with the United States and Pakistan. These differing foreign policy choices created diplomatic distance and limited their strategic cooperation for many years (Pradhan, 2013: 231-241).

New push for closer ties has been generated by the changing geopolitical landscape of the area and the rise of Saudi Arabia and India as major regional powers. India's Look West and Link West initiatives complement Saudi Arabia's efforts to expand its foreign alliances beyond conventional allies like the West and Pakistan (Chen, & Liu, 2025). Economic ties are a key part of India-Saudi relations. Saudi Arabia's large oil supply and business opportunities fit well with India's rising energy needs, big workforce and growing market. Common security concerns and similar economic goals are helping both countries build a stronger and more strategic partnership (ibid). Over time, India and Saudi Arabia have developed their traditional trade- and culture-based ties into a broad and multi-dimensional partnership. From trade, cultural exchange, and people-to-people contact, strategic cooperation has progressively expanded to cover trade and investment, energy, migration, security, defence, counterterrorism and capacity building (Hussain, 2014).

Over the past 20 years, Saudi Arabia and India's relationship has changed significantly, with a strengthening of their economic and strategic

partnership. The signing of the Delhi Declaration in 2006 and the Riyadh Declaration in 2010 laid the groundwork for greater bilateral collaboration, particularly in the energy sector (Bakr, 2021). Following these milestones, high-level reciprocal visits were made, most notably by Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi in 2016 and 2019 and Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman in 2019 and 2023, marking the beginning of a new strategic era in the relationship (Chen, & Liu, 2025). A significant outcome of this enhanced connection was the establishment of the Strategic Partnership Council (SPC), which is co-chaired by the leaders of both nations. To institutionalise collaboration, the SPC relied on two primary pillars: Economic and Investment and Political-Security-Socio-Cultural (PSSC). Each pillar, which covered subjects including infrastructure, energy, technology, agriculture and food security, was backed by Joint Working Groups (JWGs) (Embassy of India, Riyadh. 2025). The first SPC Summit, held in September 2023 during the Crown Prince's state visit to India, further elevated bilateral ties through the signing of eight Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) in diverse fields including energy, information technology, anti-corruption, investment, and desalination. Commercial relations have also seen substantial growth (ibid). Saudi Arabia was India's fifth-largest trading partner in FY 2023–2024, with a total of US\$42.98 billion in trade (ibid). Once centred on oil, the bilateral commercial partnership is now expanding into other industries like renewable energy, housing, tourism, healthcare, and entertainment (ibid). Another example of how defence cooperation has grown is the US\$225 million deal that Munitions India Limited inked to supply Saudi Arabia with artillery ammunition (ibid). Given their similar economic objectives and convergent geopolitical views, the development of India-Saudi Arabia relations demonstrates a strategic realignment and expansion of bilateral interaction (Hussain, 2023: 1-16).

During the G-20 Summit in September 2023, India and Saudi Arabia hosted the first Leader's Meeting of the Strategic Partnership Council (SPC), marking a significant step to strengthen their partnership. They focused on working together in important areas like energy, transport (railways, highways, and freight corridors), gas connections, optical fiber networks, and digital technology (Embassy of India, Riyadh. 2025). The meeting culminated in the signing of eight agreements and the establishment of two new joint working groups, underscoring the

mutual commitment to institutionalize and expand the scope of the strategic partnership.

Prime Minister Narendra Modi's visit to Saudi Arabia in 2025 marked yet another significant turning point in the growth of Indo-Saudi strategic ties and reflected the broader change in India's Gulf strategy under the "Link West Policy" (Embassy of India, Riyadh. 2025). This high-level engagement, which included participation in the India - GCC Summit and bilateral meetings with Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman, underscored a convergence of interests in energy security, infrastructure development, technological cooperation and regional stability. The visit reaffirmed both nations commitment to the Strategic Partnership Council (SPC), initiated in 2019, which now serves as the institutional backbone of their multifaceted engagement (ibid). Additionally, it represented Saudi Arabia's strategic realignment of its foreign policy in the face of changing alliances. Modi's articulation of Saudi Arabia as a "force of positivity and stability" (Bhattacharjee, 2025) aligns with India's strategic outreach under the Look West/Link West policies and complements Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 and its Look East orientation (Chen, & Liu, 2025). Additionally, Saudi Arabia's participation in such as IMEC and I2U2 shows its well-rounded multi-alignment strategy, which prioritises innovation, connectivity, and non-traditional security areas (Chen, & Liu, 2025). Modi's 2025 visit thus cemented a comprehensive and forward-looking partnership, characterized by economic pragmatism, strategic convergence, and a shared vision for a multi-polar and interconnected regional order (Khan, 2025).

Conclusion

Amidst the evolving geopolitical landscape marked by intensifying rivalries among major powers, particularly the United States, China, and Russia, Saudi Arabia has increasingly positioned itself as an influential middle power (MacGillivray, 2019: 61-80). This shift is underpinned by its strategic ambition to assert a more prominent role in the emerging multi-polar global order (Mansour, & Ahmed, 2024: 298-319). The recent shift in Saudi Arabia's foreign policy represents a marked departure from its historically security-centric alignment with the United States. A key factor behind Saudi Arabia's pivot to the East is the weakening of U.S.-Saudi strategic ties, driven by two major missteps by

recent U.S. administrations. First, the Biden administration wrongly assumed that U.S. shale oil had reduced the Gulf's significance in global energy, leading to a lowered regional focus. Second, Washington underestimated the willingness of powers like China to step in and expand their influence in the Middle East amid U.S. declining disengagement (ibid). In response to these systemic shifts, Riyadh has recalibrated its external engagements to safeguard national interests, broaden strategic options, and advance its domestic development agenda articulated in Vision 2030 (Vakil, 2025: 61-70). Central to this transformation is a strategy of multi-alignment, which entails cultivating deeper ties with emerging Asian powers most notably China and India, while simultaneously maintaining traditional partnerships with West particularly US (ibid). This emergent foreign policy framework reflects a deliberate integration of hedging behaviour, pragmatic diplomacy and economic statecraft, indicating a more autonomous and diversified approach to global engagement (Chaziza, & Lutmar, 2025).

In particular, the Sino-Saudi relationship has developed into a comprehensive strategic alliance with an emphasis on technology cooperation, infrastructure investment, and energy interdependence. The similarities between China Belt and Road Initiative and Saudi's Vision 2030 underscore the long-term convergence of development goals, particularly in areas like smart city initiatives, digital infrastructure, and transportation corridors (MacGillivray, 2019). Additionally, shared principles such as mutual non-interference and respect for sovereignty have further consolidated the strategic coherence of this bilateral relationship (Singh, 2023). Concurrently, the deepening of Saudi-India relations illustrates Riyadh's recognition of India's growing economic and geopolitical weight. The convergence of Saudi Arabia's "Look East" policy with India's "Look West" orientation has catalysed cooperation in energy, technology, infrastructure, tourism and human capital mobility (Chen & Liu, 2025). Strong bilateral synergies have been established as a result of India's sizable expatriate population in the Gulf and the Kingdom's broad economic diversification under Vision 2030. Initiatives like the India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC), which provide enhanced connectivity and mutual advantages among regions, serve as examples of this alignment (Vivek & N. D. 2024).

Importantly, Saudi Arabia's shift towards the East does not reflect a complete strategic departure from the United States. Instead, it

represents a balancing strategy typical of middle powers in a multi-polar world (Chaziza, & Lutmar, 2025). While maintaining its long-standing security ties with Washington, Saudi Arabia is increasingly asserting its autonomy in foreign policy decision-making. This dual-track approach allows Riyadh to manage great-power competition more effectively while enhancing its strategic flexibility and independence (Vakil, 2025: 61-70). Through its involvement in multilateral organisations such as SCO and BRICS, the Kingdom is consciously working to expand institutional alignments and support alternative frameworks of global governance (Vakil, 2025: 61-70). In sum, Saudi Arabia is no longer a passive stakeholder within a U.S dominated international order. It is increasingly asserting itself as a proactive middle power, leveraging multi-alignment, economic diplomacy and multilateralism to redefine its role in an evolving global landscape. The Kingdom's foreign policy shift, rooted in domestic imperatives and changing international geopolitics illustrates an adaptive strategy designed to navigate the complexities of 21st-century global politics (ibid).

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